

1 A fuzzy content-based group recommender system with
2 dynamic selection of the aggregation functions

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7 **Abstract**

Recommender systems are currently software tools that are focused on providing users with the best choices in an overloaded search space of possible options. Hence, group recommender systems have recently become an important trend in recommendation, because they aim at recommending a special type of items so-called social items, that tend to be consumed in groups such as TV programs, travel packages, etc. Among the different types of algorithms applied for group recommender systems, this paper is focused on content-based group recommender systems, as a novel group recommendation paradigm that exploits item features in the recommendation generation process. Specifically, our goal is to introduce a new content-based group recommendation approach, based on the recommendation aggregation paradigm whose main novelty is the development of a dynamic selection process of the aggregation scheme. Such an approach is centered on the identification of group's characteristics that are matching with the most appropriate function to use in the individual recommendation aggregation step. To perform such a matching, it is proposed a fuzzy decision tree induction process. The experimental evaluation shows that this scheme improves the recommendation performance of previous content-based group recommendation approaches, as well as it serves a starting point for further research based on this dynamic selection paradigm.

8 *Keywords:* content-based recommendation, group recommender systems,
9 dynamic aggregation selection, machine learning

10 **1. Introduction**

11 Recommender systems (RSs) are currently important tools in online
12 scenarios, focused on providing suggestions to users with items that best fit
13 their preferences and needs, in an overloaded product search space of possible
14 options (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005; Francesco Ricci, 2015; Yera &
15 Martínez, 2017a). Considering their working principles, RSs have been widely
16 used in several and diverse domains, such as e-commerce (Baltrunas et al.,

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Preprint submitted to Elsevier
Printed in Jaén, Spain
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17 2011), e-learning (Yera & Martínez, 2017b), e-health (Yera et al., 2019), or
18 e-tourism (Nilashi et al., 2015).

19 Two main directions have driven the development of RSs. At first, the
20 content-based recommendation paradigm (Lops et al., 2011) is focused on
21 recommending to the active user items which have similar characteristics to
22 other items previously preferred by the same user. This paradigm is then
23 mainly focused on user and item profiling for reaching a more representative
24 matching between them. On the other hand, the collaborative filtering
25 paradigm (Ekstrand et al., 2011) is focused on recommending to the current
26 user items which are preferred by other users similar to the active one.
27 Specifically, collaborative filtering methods can be classified in
28 neighborhood-based or model-based methods (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005).

29 These recommendation paradigms have been usually used to build RSs for
30 providing suggestions to individual users. However, in the last few years,
31 several kind of items that tend to be consumed by groups, have appeared in
32 recommendation contexts (Castro et al., 2018b; Dara et al., 2020). As example
33 of such items, can be cited movies and touristic routes (De Pessemier et al.,
34 2015a; Quijano-Sanchez et al., 2014). The recommendation of such items
35 requires an additional effort in relation to individual recommendation, because
36 it should manage the preferences both at the individual and the group level.
37 Such a requirement has made the development of group recommender systems
38 (GRSs) as an independent research branch in RS field (De Pessemier et al.,
39 2014).

40 Basically, GRSs are centered on aggregating the information associated to
41 the group members (De Pessemier et al., 2014). Such an aggregation can be
42 done by recommendation aggregation, in which first it is computed individual
43 recommendations for every group member, and then such recommendations are
44 combined through a recommendation aggregation approach. Alternatively, a
45 preference aggregation can also be used, where it is created a pseudo-user that
46 globally represents the preferences of the group and such a pseudo-user profile
47 is used for computing the group recommendation.

48 Using previous schemes, several research works have been focused on
49 proposing new GRSs approaches, having as common characteristic the use of a
50 collaborative filtering approach as a core of the recommendation method
51 (Castro et al., 2015, 2017; Seo et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018; Cui et al., 2020;
52 Yalcin et al., 2021), motivated by the advantages related to collaborative
53 filtering, in relation to the ability of generating recommendations using only
54 rating values. However, a well-documented shortcoming of collaborative
55 filtering is the poor performance in highly sparse recommendation scenarios
56 including cold-start (Son, 2015), considering that it depends on the presence
57 on items co-evaluated by several users for a proper performance. In contrast,
58 content-based group recommender systems (CB-GRSs, including the proposal
59 developed at the current work), usually obtain a greater success in such
60 scenario, considering that it is different from collaborative filtering because
61 they only depend on the current user preference data and the attributes'
62 information associated to the available items.

63 Nevertheless, the recent research literature reflects too few efforts for
64 boosting the use of CB-GRS. De Pessemer et al. (2014), in one of the firstly
65 documented surveys on GRS, slightly mentioned and evaluated an alternative
66 for group recommendation supported by item features for predicting user
67 preferences. However, this work is mainly focused on comparing social-choice
68 based group recommendation algorithms, and therefore do not perform an
69 in-depth analysis of the specific content-based scenario. Furthermore, the
70 architecture of a content-based recommendation algorithm has been screening
71 by Felfernig et al. (2018), but again such presentation lacks of a detailed
72 analysis of each component and experimentation. Recently, Pérez-Almaguer
73 et al. (2021) have discussed three basic design alternatives for building
74 CB-GRSs, that consider the aggregation paradigm (preferences-driven or
75 recommendations-driven), the way of aggregating recommendations
76 (ranking-based or similarity-based), the social choice-based schemes to
77 perform aggregation (e.g. average, least misery, most pleasure), and other
78 relevant design decisions. That work also explores the possible hybridization
79 between some of the presented schemes. In addition, other research works have
80 also exploited the content-based dimension in group recommendation, with a
81 greater or lesser extent (Pera & Ng, 2013; Kaššák et al., 2016).

82 This lack of works in CB-GRS in spite of its promising but not achieved
83 great performance, evidences the necessity of developing more sophisticate
84 approaches for CB-GRS, in order to obtain a better recommendation
85 performance. This paper aims at proposing a new CB-GRS scheme centered
86 on taking benefits of the nature of the data, for improving the
87 recommendation performance. Particularly, we are interested in proposing a
88 *dynamic* aggregation process, in the recommendation aggregation step in
89 CB-GRS, that will choose an appropriate aggregation function according to
90 the group's characteristics.

91 According to the Cambridge Dictionary, the word *dynamic*¹ is related to a
92 *continuous changing or developing*. In this case, we have used the *dynamic* tag
93 in our proposal, to make reference to the nature of the function used to aggregate
94 the preference of the member of the groups. In this way the selected function,
95 used with this goal, will be continuously changing based on the characteristics
96 of the current group.

97 Considering that the aggregation process can produce loss of information
98 (De Pessemer et al., 2014), the choice of the appropriate aggregation function
99 can lead to decrease the information loss and consequently improving the
100 recommendation performance.

101 In this direction, this research is driven by the following *problem definition*:
102 Given a set G of groups of users and a specific group c , find the most
103 appropriate function f to aggregate individual preferences in the
104 recommendation aggregation step inside the group, which leads to the better
105 recommendation performance in a CB-GRS framework.

¹<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/dynamic>

106 Focused on this research problem, the main contributions of our proposal
107 are:

- 108 • A new CB-GRS approach that introduces a component for the dynamic
109 selection of the recommendation aggregation function for composing
110 group recommendations. This component will receive the current group
111 features, and returns the most suitable aggregation function for such a
112 group characterization.
- 113 • The inner modeling of the dynamic selection component, done as a
114 supervised classification scenario using classification rules. Such
115 classification rules are obtained by a fuzzy classification tree using the
116 ID3 algorithm (Umanol et al., 1994; Kantarci & Nasibov, 2018). From a
117 machine learning perspective, our proposal can be seen as a
118 meta-learning approach.
- 119 • An exploratory study of group’s features in CB-GRS, such as amount of
120 ratings, minimum user’s correlation, or amount of co-rated items, that
121 could contribute to a better characterization of groups and therefore
122 improving their recommendations.
- 123 • An experimental study in order to evaluate the proposal, in contrast to
124 previous baselines.

125 The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the necessary
126 background for the proposal presentation, including content-based
127 recommendation, group recommendation, and previous works in content-based
128 group recommendation. Section 3 introduces the new CB-GRS proposal,
129 supported by the dynamic selection of the aggregation function. Subsequently,
130 a case study is also presented to show how the proposal works (Section 4).
131 Furthermore, Section 5 is focused on evaluating the proposal, discussing the
132 main findings and pointing out future works. Section 6 concludes the paper.

133 2. Background

134 This section is focused on presenting some concepts that are necessary for
135 the later proposal presentation. This content involves fundamentals on content-
136 based recommendation and group recommender systems. At last, a related
137 works section on CB-GRS will be briefly introduced.

138 2.1. Content-based recommendation

139 Since 90s, content-based recommender systems has been widely used as one
140 of the most popular recommendation approaches (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin,
141 2005). Here the recommendation process is composed of the following steps
142 (see Figure 1) :

Figure 1: General scheme of content-based recommendation

- 143 • The first step in content-based recommendation comprises the
 144 construction of an item profile $Content(i)$, that is represented by a set of
 145 features that can be explicitly or implicitly associated to the item i . A
 146 key example of explicit features, can be genre, director, country or year,
 147 in a movie recommendation scenario. On the other hand, implicit
 148 features are usually identified with techniques such as the latent
 149 semantic analysis (LSA), in domains such as news or question-answering
 150 item recommendation (Castro et al., 2019). In such an scenario, the
 151 TF-IDF approach is usually used for managing the free-text items.
 152 Specifically, such a text is converted into structured data stemming
 153 words, and after that, a vector of weights of each term is generated,
 154 according to the TF-IDF scheme. Finally, techniques such as LSA are
 155 applied for a most precise item representation (Lops et al., 2011).
- 156 • The second step of any content-based recommender systems is the user
 157 profiling. Usually, this profile $ContentBasedProfile(u)$ is built by fusing
 158 the profiles of all the items preferred by the active user u . Several
 159 strategies have been proposed for performing such a fusion, including the
 160 use of computational intelligence techniques Adomavicius & Tuzhilin
 161 (2005); Lops et al. (2011).
- 162 • Both previous profiles are used to calculate the utility of item i for user
 163 u . Such utility $v(u, i) = score(ContentBasedProfile(u), Content(i))$ is
 164 usually represented with a similarity measure such as cosine (Adomavicius
 165 & Tuzhilin, 2005). In this way, cosine metric has been used for comparing
 166 profiles linked to the vector space model (e.g. keywords-based profiles,
 167 term-based profiles), usually related to content-based recommendations
 168 (Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005; Pazzani & Billsus, 2007; de Gemmis et al.,
 169 2015). More complex approaches focused on semantic similarity have been
 170 also incorporated (Pera & Ng, 2014), however their application depends
 171 on further knowledge sources (e.g. ontologies, linked open data cloud,
 172 etc), which incorporation goes beyond the current proposal of this work
 173 that is the screening of a new CB-GRS approach.
- 174 • Finally, the top- n items with the higher utility, will be suggested for the
 175 active user u .

176 Most of research works on recommender systems have been focused on
 177 individual users. However, since the last decade there is an increasing in the

Figure 2: Group recommendation based on rating aggregation

Figure 3: Group recommendation based on recommendation aggregation

178 interest over group recommender systems (GRSs) as a novel recommendation
 179 scenario. The next section is focused on briefly presenting the fundamentals of
 180 GRSs.

181 2.2. Group recommender systems

182 The appearing of GRSs has been coupled with the need of recommending
 183 some items that are usually consumed in groups, such as movies, touristic routes,
 184 or TV programs (Castro et al., 2018c; De Pessemier et al., 2014). In such cases,
 185 it is necessary to recommend items that maximize the overall satisfaction of
 186 the group. With this goal in mind, GRSs extend individual RS, by taking into
 187 account the aggregation of information related to each individual group member.

188 The literature identifies two main paradigms in group recommendation,
 189 based on the nature of the information aggregation approach (De Pessemier
 190 et al., 2014):

- 191 • *Rating aggregation:* This approach combines the preferences of the
 192 individual users, to build a pseudo-user profile that is later used as a
 193 typical user profile to receive recommendations that in this case are
 194 delivered to the group (Figure 2).
- 195 • *Recommendation aggregation:* This approach at first generates individual
 196 recommendations for each member of the group. Such individual
 197 recommendations are then aggregated to composed the final
 198 recommendation list for the group (Figure 3).

199 The following subsection will present in further detail a recent GRS model
 200 built over the content-based recommendation paradigm (Pérez-Almaguer et al.,
 201 2021), which will be used as starting point for the proposal developed at the
 202 current paper.

Term	Meaning
u	User
i	Item
G	Group
f_k^i	Value of the feature k for item i
f_k^u	Value of the feature k for user u
f_k^G	Value of the feature k for group G
$V^k = \{v_1^k, v_2^k, v_3^k, \dots, v_p^k\}$	Possible values of the feature k in the item profile, for multivalued features
v^{ki}	Value of the feature k in the item i , for multivalued features
v^{ku}	pth value of the feature k for the user u , for multivalued features
top_u	List of top n recommendations for user u
$S_{u,i}$	Matching value between user u and item i
S_i^G	Matching value between group G and item i
I_G	Top k items recommended to the group G

Table 1: Relevant notation

Figure 4: CB-GRS based on recommendation aggregation and user-item matching values

203 *2.2.1. CB-GRS based on recommendation aggregation and user-item matching*
 204 *values*

205 This section describes in further detail, the CB-GRS approach based on
 206 recommendation aggregation and user-item matching values, initially
 207 presented at Pérez-Almaguer et al. (2021), where it was evidenced that it is
 208 able to outperform other GRS models including collaborative filtering-based.
 209 Table 1 presents the notation used across this section. This basic
 210 content-based group recommendation model (Figure 4) is composed of four
 211 phases: 1) Item modeling, 2) User modeling, 3) User-item matching value
 212 calculation, and 4) Matching value aggregation for obtaining the top k items
 213 for the group.

214 **Item modeling:** In a similar way to the typical content-based
 215 recommendation, this step is focused on representing the items to be
 216 recommended, through the modelling of a feature vector (Fig. 4). Considering
 217 that the information associated to items can be represented through different
 218 formats, here it will be considered two ways for modeling items:

- 219 1. A basic approach that considers a binary profile that contains 1 whether
 220 the item has the corresponding feature, and 0 whether the item does not
 221 contain it. Formally, items are represented as the vector $i = (f_1^i, f_2^i, \dots, f_m^i)$,
 222 where $f_k^i = 1$ whether the feature k is associated to the item i , and $f_k^i = 0$

223 otherwise.

224 2. A more sophisticated approach that considers multivalued features (Castro
225 et al., 2014). In this case, items are also represented as the vector $i =$
226 $(f_1^i, f_2^i, \dots, f_m^i)$, but here f_k^i is associated to nominal or numeric values, in
227 a domain associated to the feature k (Castro et al., 2014).

228 **User modeling:** In a similar way to items, here it will be considered two
229 approaches for user modeling.

1. An approach based on TF-IDF (Aizawa, 2003), considering the preferred items. This approach assumes a binary item profile, and here users are represented through a vector $u = (f_1^u, f_2^u, \dots, f_m^u)$. f_k^u is defined as:

$$f_k^u = FF(u, k) * IUF(k) \quad (1)$$

230 where $FF(u, k)$ is calculated as the number of items i preferred by the
231 user u , having $f_k^i = 1$ where i is any item profile built in the previous item
232 modeling phase. On the other hand, $IUF(k) = \log \frac{|U|}{UF(k)}$, being $UF(k)$
233 the number of users that have preferred any item that has the feature k ,
234 and $|U|$ the total number of users.

- 235 2. An approach that assumes the presence of multivalued features (Castro
236 et al., 2014), having the presence of nominal or numeric values in the item
237 features. In this scenario, it is necessary a new formulation of the user
238 profile (Eq. 2).

$$f_k^u = \begin{cases} \{(v_1^k, fr_{v_1^k u}), (v_2^k, fr_{v_2^k u}), (v_3^k, fr_{v_3^k u}), \dots, (v_p^k, fr_{v_p^k u})\} & , \text{ if } k \text{ is qualitative} \\ \text{average}(f_k^i) \text{ for each item } i \text{ preferred by } u, & \text{ if } k \text{ is quantitative} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

239 For items associated to qualitative features, f_k^u is formalized as a set of
240 pairs (value, frequency) composed of each one of the possible values v_p^k of
241 the feature k , and the frequency $fr_{v_p^k u}$ of such value at the feature k in
242 all the items preferred by the user u .

243 In the case of quantitative features in the items, f_k^u will be the average of
244 all the values associated to the feature, for all items preferred by the user
245 u .

246 **User-item matching value calculation:** Subsequently, the current
247 content-based GRS requires the calculation of the matching degree between
248 the corresponding user and item profile (Castro et al., 2014). Depending on
249 the presence of a binary user profile or multivalued features, a different
250 approach will be used:

1. For the binary item profiles, it will be directly used the cosine similarity function between the user and item profiles u and i (Eq. 3)

(Adomavicius & Tuzhilin, 2005), as the reference metric for content-based recommendation (see Section 2.1).

$$S_{ui} = \frac{\sum_{u,i} f_k^u * f_k^i}{\sqrt{(f_k^u)^2} \sqrt{(f_k^i)^2}} \quad (3)$$

- 251 2. In the case of the items with multivalued features, at first it is necessary to
 252 define the matching value between users and items, but in the context of a
 253 specific feature k (Eq. 4). For qualitative features, this value is calculated
 254 as fr_{v^k} , being v the associated key in the list of pairs at f_k^u , as well as
 255 the value at f_k^i . For quantitative features, this value is calculated as the
 256 inverse of the difference between f_k^u and f_k^i .

$$S_{ui}^k = \begin{cases} fr_{v^k} & , \text{ for } k \text{ qualitative} \\ \frac{1}{|f_k^u - f_k^i|} & , \text{ for } k \text{ quantitative} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

257 Such matching values are normalized independently for the qualitative
 258 and quantitative scenarios. The matching values are then denoted as S_{ui}^{k*} .
 259 At last, the overall matching value between the user u and item i is
 260 calculated as the average matching value of all the features (Eq. 5),
 261 being K the set of item features:

$$S_{ui} = \frac{\sum_{k \in K} S_{ui}^{k*}}{|K|} \quad (5)$$

262 **Matching value aggregation for obtaining the top k items for the**
 263 **group:** In the next step, the method depends on an aggregation function to
 264 obtain the matching values associated to all the group's members, and each item
 265 in the dataset.

266 The popular Average and Minimum aggregation functions will be
 267 considered in this scenario (De Pessemier et al., 2014), which have been
 268 reported in previous research in GRS as the aggregation measures that lead to
 269 a better performance regarding typical alternatives (Castro et al., 2017,
 270 2018b), and specifically focused on CB-GRS (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021).
 271 Furthermore, more sophisticated aggregation measures such as those recently
 272 discussed by Yalcin et al. (2021) will be explored in the next future. However,
 273 they are out of the scope of this work.

274 The Average and Minimum aggregation functions are formalized as follows:

1. Average: It calculates the average matching value for all the users in the group, being n the number of users.

$$S_i^G = \frac{\sum_{u \in G} S_{ui}}{n} \quad (6)$$

2. Minimum: It assumes a fairness-aware approach, and considers the lowest matching value in the group, as the aggregated matching value.

$$S_i^G = \text{Min}_u S_{ui}, \forall u \in G \quad (7)$$

275 At last, the available items are sorted in descending order according to
 276 their aggregated matching values, retrieving the top N items I_G as the
 277 recommendation list for the active group G .

278 Beyond this recently proposed CB-GRS approach, the next section will
 279 discuss the previous works developed by the research community, focused in
 280 this area with a larger or lesser extent.

281 *2.3. Related works*

282 Several works have been focused on CB-GRS in recent years, with a larger
 283 or lesser extent.

284 An early work in this direction was presented by Pera & Ng (2013),
 285 focused on proposing a GRS for movies that uses content similarity and
 286 popularity as active information for the recommendation generation. The
 287 group is modeled through an aggregation component that merges individual
 288 group’s member profiles. Such profiles are represented through the tags
 289 associated to the movies by the members themselves. A movie is then
 290 regarded as a candidate movie for recommendation, if each of the personal
 291 tags of the group, are highly similar to a tag directly associated to the movie.
 292 Offline experiments were developed to evaluate this approach.

293 Afterwards, De Pessemier et al. (2014), in a well-recognized survey on GRS,
 294 make reference to a basic scheme of CB-GRS, as one of the alternatives for the
 295 individual recommendation step in the GRS framework. Here an experimental
 296 procedure focused on comparing several GRS architectures, does not reflect any
 297 relevant finding or further analysis on the use of the content-based approach, in
 298 contrast to other collaborative filtering-based methods.

299 Kaššák et al. (2016) more recently provide a new GRS method that is based
 300 on the integration of an individual collaborative filtering and a content-based
 301 method. Here, the recommendation list initially delivered to the group’ members
 302 are aggregated for combining the output of both recommendation schemes. The
 303 authors also developed offline experiments using the Movielens dataset, as well
 304 as online experiments with real deployed systems.

305 A relevant book on group recommendation, presented by Felfernig et al.
 306 (2018), introduces a chapter section characterizing the architecture of a
 307 content-based recommendation algorithm, including stages such as
 308 content-based filtering per user, and aggregation of user-item similarities.
 309 Furthermore, it also exposes some guidelines for user and item profiling.
 310 However, the topic related to content-based at such book, lacks of a enough
 311 detailed analysis of each component and experimentation.

312 Recently, Pérez-Almaguer et al. (2021) have also discussed three basic
 313 design alternatives for building CB-GRS. Such alternatives are: 1) the

314 content-based GRS based on recommendation aggregation using individual
315 rankings, 2) the content-based GRS based on recommendation aggregation
316 and user-item matching values, and 3) the content-based GRS based on the
317 aggregation of the user profiles. They also explore the possible hybridization
318 between some of the presented schemes. The experimental framework
319 presented, includes a component for evaluating the proposals in a cold-start
320 scenario, showing that the proposals are able to outperform a collaborative
321 filtering approach in this context.

322 Other research works in the last few years have also incorporated the
323 content-based dimension in their proposal (De Pessemier et al., 2015b; Nguyen
324 & Ricci, 2018; Zhang, 2016). However, these works do not consider the
325 individual analysis and evaluation of the content-based component. Therefore,
326 they are not further described in this analysis.

327 Taking as base the CB-GRS model developed by Pérez-Almaguer et al.
328 (2021), the aim of this paper is focused on introducing a novel paradigm that
329 has not been considered previously in CB-GRS, and either in any other
330 general GRS context as far as we know. Such paradigm is the dynamic
331 selection of the recommendation aggregation function for composing group
332 recommendations, by receiving as input some current group attributes, and
333 retrieving the best aggregation function to use.

334 **3. Content-based group recommendation supported by dynamic** 335 **selection of the aggregation function**

336 This section introduces a novel procedure for building CB-GRSs based on *the*
337 *user-item matching value aggregation step for calculating the global preferences*
338 *of the group*. While the previous reported works statically use a predefined
339 aggregation function for this stage, here it is proposed the use of a dynamic
340 selection process of the aggregation function to be considered in the aggregation
341 of the group’s member preferences to obtain the final recommendations (Figure
342 5). This process is supported through the use of rules obtained from a fuzzy
343 decision tree that is built over some characteristics of the group that would
344 influence the performance of the different aggregation functions.

345 To reach this goal, this process is composed of three phases: dataset building,
346 fuzzy decision tree induction, and fuzzy rules building and classification (Figure
347 6):

- 348 1. *Dataset building*: This phase is focused on gathering all the necessary data
349 for the subsequent phases. It includes the group attributes selection and
350 the training set building.
- 351 2. *Fuzzy decision tree induction*: This phase is focused on building the fuzzy
352 decision tree, taking as input the built training set represented by the
353 groups’ profile composed of the group attribute values.
- 354 3. *Fuzzy rules building and classification*: This phase is focused on using the
355 built decision tree for obtaining fuzzy rules that will compose a rule-based

Figure 5: Screening the novel procedure for building CB-GRSs

Figure 6: The stages of the process focused on the dynamic selection of the aggregation function

356 classifier. Such classifier will allow, for a specific group, to determine
 357 the most appropriate aggregation function for aggregating its member
 358 preferences in the group recommendation task.

359 In detail, we propose the modeling of a direct matching between a set of
 360 group features and such proper aggregation function, by using a fuzzy supervised
 361 classification approach. Here, we incorporate a previously-trained supervised
 362 classifier that receives as input the attributes of the active group, and provides
 363 as output which aggregation function (De Pessemier et al., 2014), is the most
 364 appropriated one to be used for aggregating the matching values associated to
 365 each individual of the group.

366 With this aim, we have selected a fuzzy ID3 classifier (Umanol et al., 1994;
 367 Kantarci & Nasibov, 2018), which has several advantages over the other
 368 alternatives, considering that it is a white-box and therefore an
 369 understandable and interpretable model (Arrieta et al., 2020), and that also is
 370 able to manage uncertainty through the use of fuzzy logic which is necessary
 371 in recommender systems (Yera & Martínez, 2017a).

372 Figure 7 depicts this process, for illustrating its working principle. Here it
 373 is assumed two groups' features X and Y , which are characterized by three
 374 linguistic terms *low*, *medium*, and *high*. The objective of the current proposal

Figure 7: Overview of the fuzzy decision tree induction and classification process, for supporting the dynamic selection of the aggregation function

375 is the building of a fuzzy decision tree like the presented in the left box of
 376 Figure 7, which leads to the classification rules presented in the right box.
 377 Based on the values of the attributes X and Y for each group, these rules make
 378 decision about which aggregation function is better for aggregating the
 379 individual preferences. In this proposal the decision is between Average or
 380 Minimum operators, considering they have had a good performance in
 381 previous CB-GRS scenarios (see Section 2.2.1).

382 This approach is further detailed in the coming subsections.

383 3.1. Dataset building

384 The dataset building phase comprises all the necessary data management
 385 operations as a previous step for the fuzzy decision tree induction. This phase
 386 is composed of two steps, 1) Group attributes selection, and 2) Training set
 387 building.

388 **Group attributes selection:** The first step of this phase, requires the
 389 identification of attributes for characterizing groups. While the
 390 features/attributes extraction paradigm has been widely used in several
 391 recommender systems models Koren et al. (2009), the attributes extracted by
 392 such models usually do not have a clear semantic meaning Isinkaye (2021). In
 393 contrast, in our current contribution it is necessary to characterize groups
 394 through attributes with a clear semantic meaning, regarding they will be
 395 incorporated later in a white-box computational model that require to
 396 understand their nature (i.e. a fuzzy decision tree, see Figure 7).

397 For this reason, in the current contribution we characterize groups through
 398 an attribute building process that follows the common sense and also previous
 399 criteria by other authors, for proposing attributes that characterize groups in a
 400 GRS scenario. The analysis of the research literature also identifies the
 401 development of similar attributes building procedure in previous works, such
 402 as Jankiewicz et al. (2019) in the travel recommendation domain, Janusz et al.

Term	Meaning
M	Minimum correlation between any pair of group members
A	Amount of ratings overall, provided by all the group members
C	Amount of co-rated items by all the users in the group
AV	The rating average of the group

Table 2: Attributes for characterizing the groups

403 (2018) in job recommendation, Xie et al. (2012) in music preference prediction,
 404 or Zeeshan et al. (2021) in multi-criteria recommendation.

405 In this way, in the current work the following group attributes are explored:
 406 1) the minimum correlation between any pair of group members (M), 2) the
 407 amount of ratings provided by the group (A), 3) the amount of co-rated items
 408 by all the users (C), and 4) the rating average of the group (AV) (see Table 2).
 409 Previous works have suggested that such kind of information can be used for
 410 characterizing groups in a distinguishable way, and that the proper aggregation
 411 approach in this context, could depend on such features (Baltrunas et al., 2010;
 412 De Pessemier et al., 2014; Boratto et al., 2015; Castro et al., 2017, 2018a).

413 Equation 8 formalizes the minimum correlation between any pair of group
 414 members (M). In this case, for each pair of users in the group, the Pearson’s
 415 correlation coefficient considering their rating values is calculated. Finally, the
 416 group is characterized as the minimum of such correlation values.

$$M(G) = \min \text{corr}(u, v), \forall u, v \in G \quad (8)$$

417 For each group, the calculation of this value $M(G)$ has a computational cost
 418 $O(n \log n)$, being n the amount of ratings for the user with the larger list of
 419 ratings.

420 Equation 9, on the other hand, formalizes the amount of ratings elicited by
 421 the group (A), which can be obtained in a direct way. Here R_u is the set of the
 422 ratings provided by the user u .

$$A(G) = \sum_{u \in G} |R_u| \quad (9)$$

423 For each group, the calculation of this value $A(G)$ has a computational cost
 424 $O(n)$, being n the amount of ratings for the user with the larger list of ratings.

425 Subsequently, the amount of co-rated items (C) is formalized in Equation
 426 10. In this case, this attribute is focused on the amount of items that has been
 427 evaluated by all the members of the group.

$$C(G) = |I_c|, \text{ where } I_c = \{i : \forall_{u \in G} r_{ui} \in R\} \quad (10)$$

428 For each group, the calculation of this value $C(G)$ has a computational cost
 429 $O(n \log n)$, being n the amount of ratings for the user with the larger list of
 430 ratings. Considering the computational cost viewpoint, the reaching of $C(G)$
 431 could be identified as a subtask of the $M(G)$ calculation.

432 Finally, Equation 11 formalizes the simple average (AV) of all the ratings
 433 in the group’s members, as the fourth group attribute. Here, R is the set of
 434 ratings provided by all the members in the group (Equation 12).

$$AV(G) = \frac{\sum_{r_{ui} \in R} r_{ui}}{|R|} \quad (11)$$

$$R = \cup_{u \in G} R_u \quad (12)$$

435 For each group, the calculation of this value $AV(G)$ has a computational
 436 cost $O(n \log n)$, being n the amount of ratings for the user with the larger list of
 437 ratings.

438 In addition to the low computational cost associated to the calculation of
 439 these four features, it is worthy to note that in practice, their values were
 440 instantaneously obtained for all experimental scenarios developed in this paper
 441 (Section 5).

442 Without loss of generality, we assume that the attribute values
 443 characterizing each group, are already normalized (into the range $[0,1]$),
 444 facilitating the subsequent stages of the proposal.

445 *Remark 1:* For complementing the reported evidence on the suitability of
 446 these attributes, Section 5.4 presents an exploratory study for characterizing
 447 them in real RS datasets. This study concludes that they are an appropriate
 448 way for identifying different kind of groups, being such fact relevant for the
 449 personalized recommendation delivery.

450 **Training set building:** From the identified attributes for characterizing
 451 groups, the training set building process is focused on building a dataset able
 452 to execute a supervised classification task using such attributes as features, and
 453 the most appropriate aggregation function as target class. It is developed by
 454 the following procedure:

- 455 1. At first, several groups from the available data are sampled. It is expected
 456 that each sampled group is characterized by several numeric attributes,
 457 having a close relationship with the member’s ratings. Therefore, initially
 458 is necessary to compute and normalize the four attribute values associated
 459 to the group. The values of such attributes M, A, C, AV , are used for
 460 characterizing groups in a supervised classification scenario deployed here.
- 461 2. Once each sampled group is characterized by their corresponding
 462 attributes values, it is necessary to find the class
 463 $C \in \{Average, Minimum\}$ associated to each group. These two classes
 464 have been considered because previous works have reported that they
 465 performed well in a CB-GRS scenario (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021).
 466 The class in this case represents the aggregation function that performs
 467 best at the matching value aggregation step for obtaining the top k items
 468 for the group, presented at Section 2.2.1. To find it, we use the following
 469 steps:

- 470 • Execute twice the core content-based GRS already presented at
471 Section 2.2.1 for the current group and sampled dataset, initially
472 using the average aggregation and at second using minimum
473 aggregation.
- 474 • Compare both recommendation approaches according to some
475 specific evaluation method. In this case, it will be used the
476 precision metric which has been an appropriate metric for
477 characterizing content-based GRS, according to the most recent
478 literature (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021). In the future, other
479 metrics such as NDCG, or even a multicriteria approach
480 simultaneously considering several metrics, will be developed.
- 481 • Finally, the class of the current group is tagged as the aggregation
482 scheme (average or minimum) that performs best according to the
483 evaluation metric. Future works will also consider other aggregation
484 operators like the maximum aggregation in this context
485 (De Pessemier et al., 2014). However, we discard it at this moment
486 because it leads to poor recommendation performance in recent
487 evaluations done by the literature (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021).

488 Overall, this phase retrieves as output a dataset containing several group
489 profiles, each one characterized by their associated attribute values.
490 Furthermore, each group is also linked to a class value that represents the
491 aggregation function that leads to the best recommendation performance (i.e.
492 average or minimum). This dataset is used as input for the next phase of the
493 proposal, which is the fuzzy decision tree induction.

494 3.2. Fuzzy decision tree induction

495 Here, it is presenting the fuzzy decision tree induction process, made in this
496 case over the group characterization, built in the previous step.

497 This phase assumes D as fuzzy set, that is characterized by a membership
498 value for each group G in the dataset. (Initially with membership 1 for all
499 groups, at the root of the tree). Furthermore, each group is represented by
500 four numerical values respectively for attributes $A_i \in \{M, A, C, AV\}$, and one
501 class $C_k \in \{Average, Minimum\}$ (see Section 2.2.1 for justifying the classes
502 selection). In addition, assumes D^{C_k} as a fuzzy subset of D , where $\mu_{D^{C_k}}(G) =$
503 $\mu_D(G)$ if the class of G is C_k , and $\mu_{D^{C_k}}(G) = 0$ otherwise. Finally, $|D^{C_k}|$ is the
504 cardinality of the fuzzy set D^{C_k} , defined as the sum of the membership value
505 of each associated object (Umanol et al., 1994).

506 In the current scenario, it is considered that each attribute A_i , always
507 represented by numerical values, will be characterized by three triangular
508 fuzzy sets *low*, *medium*, and *high* (Figure 8). More complex fuzzy
509 representations could be also used, for modeling this membership. Therefore,
510 each group is then characterized by the membership values for each mentioned
511 fuzzy sets, considering each of the four attributes (Table 3).

512 The algorithm for constructing the fuzzy decision tree is then as follows:

g_1	$(\mu_{M,low}(g_1), \mu_{M,medium}(g_1), \mu_{M,high}(g_1), \mu_{A,low}(g_1), \mu_{A,medium}(g_1), \mu_{A,high}(g_1),$ $\mu_{C,low}(g_1), \mu_{C,medium}(g_1), \mu_{C,high}(g_1), \mu_{AV,low}(g_1), \mu_{AV,medium}(g_1), \mu_{AV,high}(g_1))$
g_2	$(\mu_{M,low}(g_2), \mu_{M,medium}(g_2), \mu_{M,high}(g_2), \mu_{A,low}(g_2), \mu_{A,medium}(g_2), \mu_{A,high}(g_2),$ $\mu_{C,low}(g_2), \mu_{C,medium}(g_2), \mu_{C,high}(g_2), \mu_{AV,low}(g_2), \mu_{AV,medium}(g_2), \mu_{AV,high}(g_2))$
...	...

Table 3: Representation of each group, using the four attributes and the corresponding fuzzy sets *low*, *medium*, and *high*.

Figure 8: Membership functions

513 1. Initially build the root node which is composed of all the data, and then
514 is represented as a fuzzy set with all the objects having 1 as membership
515 value.

516 2. If a candidate node t with a fuzzy set of data D verifies:

(a) If the relative frequency of some class $C_k \in Average, Minimum$ in the dataset is over some threshold θ_r :

$$\frac{|D^{C_k}|}{|D|} \geq \theta_r \quad (13)$$

(b) Or the cardinality of the dataset is under a given threshold:

$$|D| \leq \theta_n \quad (14)$$

517 (c) Or there are no attributes for more classification

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Then it is a leaf node and the weight of each class in this leaf is assigned as the cardinality $|D^{C_k}|$ of the corresponding class C_k in such node.

3. Otherwise, the new decision node is constructed as follows, by selecting the attribute that maximizes the information gain $G(A_i, D)$. Therefore, for each attribute $A_i \in \{M, A, C, AV\}$ not considered before, calculate the information gain $G(A_i, D)$ (Eqs 15-19) and select the attribute A_{max} that maximizes it:

$$G(A_i, D) = I(D) - E(A_i, D) \quad (15)$$

where,

$$I(D) = - \sum_{k=1}^n (p_k * \log_2 p_k) \quad (16)$$

$$E(A_i, D) = \sum_{j=1}^m (p_{ij} * I(D_{A_i, j})) \quad (17)$$

$$p_k = \frac{|D^{C_k}|}{|D|} \quad (18)$$

$$p_{ij} = \frac{|D_{A_i, j}|}{\sum_{l=1}^m |D_{A_i, l}|} \quad (19)$$

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Here $I(D)$ at Eq. (16) is the total entropy of certain dataset D , while $E(A_i, D)$ at Eq. (17) is the fuzzy classification entropy of the attribute A_i . p_k is the relative frequency of the class C_k in the dataset, and p_{ij} is the relative frequency of all objects within the branch associated to the corresponding linguistic label j and attribute A_i , into each class. $D_{A_i, j}$ is the fuzzy subset which membership is represented by the linguistic term $j \in \{low, medium, high\}$ linked to the group attribute $A_i \in \{M, A, C, AV\}$.

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4. Once the attribute A_{max} that maximizes the information gain is chosen, **the decision node D is divided into three fuzzy subsets $D_{A_{max}, low}$, $D_{A_{max}, medium}$, $D_{A_{max}, high}$ according to such attribute**, each subset for each linguistic label that characterizes such attribute. The membership value of each group g to $D_{A_{max}, j}$ ($j \in \{low, medium, high\}$), is then the product of the membership value of g to D , and the value $\mu_{A_{max}, j}(g)$ associated to A_{max} in D .

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5. Generate new nodes t_1, t_2, t_3 for fuzzy subsets $D_{A_{max}, low}$, $D_{A_{max}, medium}$, $D_{A_{max}, high}$, labelling with each corresponding linguistic term $j \in \{low, medium, high\}$, to each edge that connect them with D .

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539

6. For each fuzzy subset $D_{A_{max}, low}$, $D_{A_{max}, medium}$, $D_{A_{max}, high}$, repeat recursively this algorithm from step 2.

540 Once the fuzzy decision tree is generated, it will be used in the next phase of
 541 the proposal as the base of the fuzzy rules building and classification processes.

542 3.3. Fuzzy rules building and classification

543 Once the fuzzy decision tree is built, their branches lead to the creation of
 544 decision rules which are directly used for classification. The rules are
 545 formulated as follows, considering for every branch all the associated attributes
 546 and linguistic terms at the nodes from the root, to the leaf of the branch.

Rule R = If A_{i1} is $j1$ and ... and If A_{in} is jn then Class = C_k with weight W_k
 (20)

547 Here $A_{i1} \in \{M, A, C, AV\}$ is an attribute used for identifying groups, and
 548 $j1 \in \{low, medium, high\}$ is a linguistic term for representing the corresponding
 549 fuzzy set for characterizing such attribute, linked to the corresponding path in
 550 the inferred decision tree. $C_k \in \{Average, Minimum\}$ is the class label in the
 551 leaf node. W_k is the weight of the leaf node, calculate through the addition of
 552 the membership of all objects of class k at this node.

553 In this context, and assuming a new group g , the fuzzy classification is
 554 performed as follows:

1. Matching degree: Here, the activation degree of the if part for a rule R , with the group g , is calculated as:

$$\mu_R(g) = T(\mu_{A_{i1},j1}(g), \mu_{A_{i2},j2}(g), \dots, \mu_{A_{in},jn}(g)) \quad (21)$$

555 where $\mu_{A_i,j}(g)$ is the membership degree of the value of the
 556 $A_i \in \{M, A, C, AV\}$ attribute of the example g with the fuzzy set
 557 associated to the same attribute A_i and the linguistic term
 558 $j \in \{low, medium, high\}$, at the corresponding antecedent of the rule R .
 559 T is a T-norm (Pedrycz, 1993).

2. Association degree: The degree of the association of the group g with each rule R at the rule base and for the class k is computed as:

$$b_{Rk}(g) = T(\mu_R(g), W_k) \quad (22)$$

560 where W_k is the weight of the rule R for the class k (i.e. the rule weight,
 561 see Eq. 20). T is a T-norm (Pedrycz, 1993).

3. Confidence degree: Finally, the confidence degree of each class is calculated by aggregating the association degrees of the rules of that class through the use of an operator T^* , being a T-conorm (Pedrycz, 1993):

$$conf_k(g) = T^*(b_{1k}(g), b_{2k}(g), b_{3k}(g), \dots, b_{Rk}(g)) \quad (23)$$

562 Here $b_{Rk}(g)$, is the association degree of the group g to the class k
 563 according to the rule R .

564 The group g is then classified as the class k with the highest confidence
565 degree $conf_k(g)$, considering all the rules identified at the decision tree
566 induction process.

567 Section 4 will demonstrate the use of the procedure presented here, in a GRS
568 scenario.

569 3.4. Algorithmic overview of the approach

570 As summary, Algorithm 1 presents an overview of the current approach,
571 receiving as input the set of groups G at the GRS, and the current group c for
572 finding the most appropriate aggregation function, which is the output of the
573 approach.

574 At first, Lines 4-12 are focused on the dataset building phase, calculating for
575 each group the values of the four attributes for characterizing them, as well as
576 the aggregation function that performs better in a recommendation generation
577 process. Finally, a tuple with this information is added to a dataset D (Line
578 12) that is used in the subsequent stages of the method.

579 Furthermore, Line 13 obtains the fuzzy decision tree T using such dataset
580 D . Subsequently, such tree is used for building the classification rules that will
581 allow to obtain, for any group of users characterized by the four mentioned
582 attributes, the most appropriate aggregation function to be used (Lines 14-16).

583 Finally, such set of rules is used for finding the referred aggregation function
584 for the current group c (Line 17), retrieving it as the output of the method (Line
585 18).

586 Algorithm 1 has presented all the phases of the proposal in order to expose
587 a compact overview of its working principle. However, it is also worthy to note
588 that in practice, the dataset building, tree induction, and rules building phases
589 (Lines 4-16) can be executed previously in an offline stage, and stored the rules
590 set R . In this way, in the real-time recommendation generation for a specific
591 group c , it would be directly executed the fuzzy classification step (Line 17),
592 using the stored rules set.

593 In the next sections it will be presented a case study and the evaluation of
594 an experimental protocol associated to the current proposal.

595 4. Case study

596 This subsection develops and describes a case study showing how the
597 algorithm presented in the previous subsection can be used for the dynamic
598 selection of the most appropriate function for individual recommendation
599 aggregation.

600 4.1. Fuzzy decision tree induction

601 At first, Table 4 presents a dataset that can be obtained through the
602 methodology at Section 3.1, that contains five groups. In this case, for
603 simplicity it is composed of 3 attributes which are minimum correlation

Algorithm 1 Algorithmic overview of the approach

```
1: procedure FUZZY CB-GRS( $a, b$ )
2:   Input:  $c$ -currentGroup,  $G$ -set of groups
3:   Output: selectedAggFunction- Aggregation function to be used in the
   current group
4:   for all group  $g$  in  $G$  do
5:      $M_g = \text{MinimumCorrelation}(g)$ 
6:      $A_g = \text{AmountGroupR}(g)$ 
7:      $C_g = \text{CoRated}(g)$ 
8:      $AV_g = \text{RatingAverage}(g)$ 
9:     Calculate recommendation performance with average preference
   aggregation for group  $g$ 
10:    Calculate recommendation performance with minimum preference
   aggregation for group  $g$ 
11:    Assign  $Class_g$  as the aggregation scheme that performs better
12:    Add tuple  $(M_g, A_g, C_g, AV_g, Class_g)$  to the dataset  $D$ 
13:     $T = \text{ObtainFuzzyDecisionTree}(D)$ 
14:    for all path  $p$  from root to the leaves nodes in  $T$  do
15:      Build the associated classification rules  $r$ 
16:      Add  $r$  to the rules set  $R$ 
17:    selectedAggFunction = Rule-basedClassifier( $R, c$ )
18:    return selectedAggFunction
```

604 (MinCorr, i.e. M), amount of ratings in the group (AmountGroupR, i.e. A)
605 and average amount of co-rated items across users (Co-RatedAvg, i.e. C). Two
606 classes are considered, the average aggregation and the minimum aggregation
607 (Avg, and Min). In the next future it will be additionally considered more
608 sophisticated aggregation schemes such as the Additive Utilitarian hybridized
609 with the Approval Voting (Yalcin et al., 2021), as well as the Agreement
610 without Uncertainty approach (Yalcin et al., 2021). However, they are out of
611 the scope of this work.

612 Table 4 shows the value of each attribute at the five objects. Furthermore,
613 it contains the membership value of each object, to the three previously
614 mentioned fuzzy sets A_{low} , A_{medium} , A_{high} , for each attribute A (referred at
615 the previous Section 3.2). Subsequently, in this section is developed the
616 decision tree induction associated to such dataset, which is presented in Figure
617 9. Furthermore, as parameters it is considered $\theta_r = 0.9$, (i.e. a node is not
618 expanded when the cardinality of some class over the total cardinality exceeds
619 0.9); and $\theta_n = 0.01$, (i.e. a node is not expanded when its fuzzy cardinality in
620 under 0.01). We use this value for θ_n for guaranteeing the generation of a
621 decision tree as large as possible, with demonstrative proposals. Larger values
622 of θ_n would lead to a less-expanded decision tree. However, they are not
623 included here due to space reasons.

624 **Root node:** Following the steps of the decision tree induction procedure

	MinCorr(M)	AmountGroupR(A)	Co-RatedAvg(C)	Class
g_1	0.3 $\mu_{M,low}(g_1) = 0.24$ $\mu_{M,medium}(g_1) = 0.76$ $\mu_{M,high}(g_1) = 0$	300 $\mu_{A,low}(g_1) = 0$ $\mu_{A,medium}(g_1) = 0.9$ $\mu_{A,high}(g_1) = 0.1$	20 $\mu_{C,low}(g_1) = 0$ $\mu_{C,medium}(g_1) = 0.9$ $\mu_{C,high}(g_1) = 0.1$	Avg
g_2	0.7 $\mu_{M,low}(g_2) = 0$ $\mu_{M,medium}(g_2) = 0$ $\mu_{M,high}(g_2) = 1$	150 $\mu_{A,low}(g_2) = 0.82$ $\mu_{A,medium}(g_2) = 0.18$ $\mu_{A,high}(g_2) = 0$	10 $\mu_{C,low}(g_2) = 0.82$ $\mu_{C,medium}(g_2) = 0.18$ $\mu_{C,high}(g_2) = 0$	Avg
g_3	0.05 $\mu_{M,low}(g_3) = 1$ $\mu_{M,medium}(g_3) = 0$ $\mu_{M,high}(g_3) = 0$	450 $\mu_{A,low}(g_3) = 0$ $\mu_{A,medium}(g_3) = 0$ $\mu_{A,high}(g_3) = 1$	30 $\mu_{C,low}(g_3) = 0$ $\mu_{C,medium}(g_3) = 0$ $\mu_{C,high}(g_3) = 1$	Min
g_4	0.1 $\mu_{M,low}(g_4) = 0.84$ $\mu_{M,medium}(g_4) = 0.16$ $\mu_{M,high}(g_4) = 0$	120 $\mu_{A,low}(g_4) = 1$ $\mu_{A,medium}(g_4) = 0$ $\mu_{A,high}(g_4) = 0$	8 $\mu_{C,low}(g_4) = 1$ $\mu_{C,medium}(g_4) = 0$ $\mu_{C,high}(g_4) = 0$	Min
g_5	0.5 $\mu_{M,low}(g_5) = 0$ $\mu_{M,medium}(g_5) = 0.62$ $\mu_{M,high}(g_5) = 0.38$	400 $\mu_{A,low}(g_5) = 0$ $\mu_{A,medium}(g_5) = 0.3$ $\mu_{A,high}(g_5) = 0.7$	15 $\mu_{C,low}(g_5) = 0.36$ $\mu_{C,medium}(g_5) = 0.64$ $\mu_{C,high}(g_5) = 0$	Min

Table 4: Case study for the dynamic selection of the aggregation function

625 presented above, at first it is considered the current root node with the five
626 objects with membership $\mu_n(g) = 1$. Therefore, the calculation of information
627 amount $I(D)$ of such node (Eq. 16) and the information gain $G(A, D)$ at each
628 attribute A (Eq. 15), lead to the following results:

$$I(D) = 0.971, \quad G(M, D) = 0.2143, \quad G(A, D) = 0.2897, \quad G(C, D) = 0.1301 \quad (24)$$

629 Here the attribute that maximizes the information gain is the amount of
630 ratings in the group (AmountGroupR, A). Then, according to the steps 4 and 5
631 at Section 3.2, the set of objects in the current root node is divided in three fuzzy
632 subsets, characterized by the membership functions associated to such attribute
633 A. Three new nodes are respectively created for such subsets. At Figure 9, these
634 nodes are labeled as (a_{low}) , (a_{med}) , and (a_{high}) .

635 **Node a_{low} :** Analyzing the node a_{low} , characterized by the objects g_2
636 ($\mu_n(g_2) = 0.82$) and g_4 ($\mu_n(g_4) = 1$). Here it is analyzed the information
637 amount $I(D_{A_{low}})$ of this node, as well as the information gain for the
638 remaining attributes M and C :

$$I(D_{A_{low}}) = 0.993, \quad G(M, D_{A_{low}}) = 0.993, \quad G(C, D_{A_{low}}) = 0.0998 \quad (25)$$

639 which lead to the selection of the attribute M at this stage.

640 This leads to the expansion of the nodes (a_{low}, m_{low}) , (a_{low}, m_{med}) , and
641 (a_{low}, m_{high}) (see Figure 9).

642 These three nodes have only one associated object, therefore the process

Figure 9: Fuzzy decision tree of the dataset at Table 4, for the dynamic selection of the aggregation function

643 stops at this stage considering that here the cardinality of its associated class is
 644 1. Such nodes are then considered as leaves nodes, having as their corresponding
 645 classes, the class associated to their objects.

646 **Node a_{med} :** This node is characterized by the objects ($\mu_n(g_1) = 0.9$), g_2
 647 ($\mu_n(g_2) = 0.18$), and g_5 ($\mu_n(g_5) = 0.3$). In this node, the attributes M and C
 648 are also analyzed:

$$I(D_{A_{med}}) = 0.755, \quad G(M, D_{A_{med}}) = 0.0779, \quad G(C, D_{A_{med}}) = 0.0542 \quad (26)$$

649 which lead, in a similar way to node a_{low} , to the selection of the attribute
 650 M at this stage.

651 This leads to the expansion of the nodes (a_{med}, m_{low}) , (a_{med}, m_{med}) , and
 652 (a_{med}, m_{high}) (see Figure 9).

653 Here the node (a_{med}, m_{low}) has only one associated object, therefore the
 654 process stops at this stage. On the other hand, the remaining two nodes are
 655 analyzed as follows.

656 **Node (a_{med}, m_{med}) :** This node is characterized by two objects (g_1
 657 ($\mu_n(g_1) = 0.684$), g_5 ($\mu_n(g_5) = 0.186$)). It is then expanded through the
 658 remaining attribute C (see Figure 9), composing the three nodes
 659 $(a_{med}, m_{med}, c_{low})$, $(a_{med}, m_{med}, c_{med})$, and $(a_{med}, m_{med}, c_{high})$. These new
 660 nodes are not expanded because there are not any more attributes.

661 **Node (a_{med}, m_{high}) :** This node is characterized by two objects (g_2
 662 ($\mu_n(g_2) = 0.18$), g_5 ($\mu_n(g_5) = 0.114$)). It is then expanded through the

R_1	if A is low and M is low, then Class=Min with W=0.84
R_2	if A is low and M is medium, then Class=Min with W=0.16
R_3	if A is low and M is high, then Class=Avg with W=0.82
R_4	if A is medium and M is low, then Class=Avg with W=0.216
R_5	if A is medium and M is medium and C is low, then Class=Min with W=0.066
R_6	if A is medium and M is medium and C is medium, then Class=Avg with W=0.616, and Class=Min with W=0.119
R_7	if A is medium and M is medium and C is high, then Class=Avg with W=0.0684
R_8	if A is medium and M is high and C is low, then Class=Avg with W=0.1476, and Class=Min with W=0.041
R_9	if A is medium and M is high and C is medium, then Class=Avg with W=0.0324, and Class=Min with W=0.073
R_{10}	if A is high, then Class=Avg with W=0.1, and Class=Min with W=1.7

Table 5: Rules associated to the decision tree at Figure 9

663 remaining attribute C (see Figure 9), composing the two nodes
664 $(a_{med}, m_{high}, c_{low})$ and $(a_{med}, m_{high}, c_{med})$. These new nodes are not expanded
665 because there are not any more attributes. The node $(a_{med}, m_{high}, c_{high})$ is
666 not included because it does not contains any object with membership values
667 different from zero (see Figure 9).

668 **Node a_{high} :** This node is characterized by the objects g_1 ($\mu_n(g_1) = 0.1$),
669 g_3 ($\mu_n(g_3) = 1$), and g_5 ($\mu_n(g_5) = 0.7$). At such node, it is verified the stop
670 condition (a) at the second step of the procedure, regarding that for the class
671 avg, $|D^{avg}|/|D| = 0.944 > 0.9$, assuming that $\theta_r = 0.9$. Therefore this node is
672 not expanded.

673 This stage finishes the induction of the fuzzy decision tree presented at Figure
674 9. According to Section 3.3, such tree leads to the rules based on the class of
675 the objects at the leaves nodes, presented at Table 5

676 4.2. Fuzzy classification

677 Based on the rules presented at Table 5, as example it will be classified the
678 group o presented at Table 6. The first row of the table presents the values of
679 the attributes of the object, while the remaining rows present the membership
680 values associated to the three fuzzy sets (Fig. 8) that characterize each attribute
681 according to the current dataset presented at Table 6.

682 Subsequently, Table 7 illustrates the three stages of the classification
683 procedure at Section 3.3. At the first stage, it is calculated the matching
684 degree of the object with the antecedents of the rules. At Table 7, it is only
685 presented the rules with a matching degree different from 0, which are R_6 , R_7 ,
686 R_9 , and R_{10} . Furthermore, in the next stage it is calculated the association of
687 the object with the corresponding class linked to the rule. Here it is worthy to

	MinCorr(M)	AmountGroupR(A)	Co-RatedAvg(C)
	0.4	300	25
o	$\mu_{M,low}(o) = 0$	$\mu_{A,low}(o) = 0$	$\mu_{C,low}(o) = 0$
	$\mu_{M,medium}(o) = 0.92$	$\mu_{A,medium}(o) = 0.9$	$\mu_{C,medium}(o) = 0.46$
	$\mu_{M,high}(o) = 0.08$	$\mu_{A,high}(o) = 0.1$	$\mu_{C,high}(o) = 0.54$

Table 6: Classification example

Stage 1	$\mu_{R_6}(o) = 0.46, \mu_{R_7}(o) = 0.54, \mu_{R_9}(o) = 0.08, \mu_{R_{10}}(o) = 0.1$
	Class Avg
	$b_{R_6,avg} = T(\mu_{R_6}(o), RW_6^{avg}) = T(0.46, 0.616) = 0.46$
	$b_{R_7,avg} = T(\mu_{R_7}(o), RW_7^{avg}) = T(0.54, 0.0684) = 0.0684$
	$b_{R_9,avg} = T(\mu_{R_9}(o), RW_9^{avg}) = T(0.08, 0.0324) = 0.0324$
Stage 2	$b_{R_{10},avg} = T(\mu_{R_{10}}(o), RW_{10}^{avg}) = T(0.1, 0.1) = 0.1$
	Class Min
	$b_{R_6,min} = T(\mu_{R_6}(o), RW_6^{min}) = T(0.46, 0.119) = 0.119$
	$b_{R_9,min} = T(\mu_{R_9}(o), RW_9^{min}) = T(0.08, 0.073) = 0.073$
	$b_{R_{10},min} = T(\mu_{R_{10}}(o), RW_{10}^{min}) = T(0.1, 1.7) = 0.1$
Stage 3	$conf_{avg}(o) = T^*(b_{R_6,avg}, b_{R_7,avg}, b_{R_9,avg}, b_{R_{10},avg}) = 0.46$
	$conf_{min}(o) = T^*(b_{R_6,min}, b_{R_9,min}, b_{R_{10},min}) = 0.119$
	$class_o = avg$

Table 7: Classification procedure

688 note that in three of the four considered rules, there is a contribution value of
689 the rule to both classes, therefore both values are individually computed at
690 each individual class processing. Both stages depend on a T-norm, being used
691 the *min* operator in this scenario.

692 Finally, in the last stage at Table 7, it is calculated the confidence degree of
693 each class, by using a T-conorm for joining the association degree of each rule,
694 associated to each independent class. Here it is used the *max* operator as T-
695 conorm. As final result it is reached that the *avg* class has a higher confidence;
696 therefore the object o is classified with the *avg* class.

697 Then, it means that the *avg* aggregation approach seems to be the best
698 option for aggregating individual recommendations in the group characterized
699 by the attributes associated to the object o .

700 5. Experiments

701 This section is focused on evaluating the content-based GRS presented across
702 this paper. At first, they are presented the datasets (Section 5.1), the evaluation
703 metric (Section 5.2), and the evaluation protocol used in the experimentation
704 (Section 5.3). Subsequently, for each dataset it is presented an exploratory
705 study on the values of such attributes across the datasets (Section 5.4); and it is
706 then evaluated the performance of the proposal comparing it against baselines
707 (Section 5.5). A discussion on the results is also included (Section 5.6), as well
708 as future works to expand the current proposal (Section 5.7).

709 *5.1. Datasets*

710 This work is supported by two recognized datasets that have been used for
711 studying content-based recommendation systems (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021).

- 712 • **Movielens 100K**, having 943 users, 1682 movies, and 100000 ratings in
713 the range [1,5] (Harper & Konstan, 2015). Movies are classified
714 considering 19 possible genres, including Action, Sci-Fi, Comedy,
715 Adventure, etc. In this context, the item profile is represented as a
716 binary vector composed of 19 dimensions, having 1 whether the
717 corresponding genre is associated to the movie, and 0 otherwise. This
718 dataset is used to evaluate the binary item profile approach.
- 719 • **HetRec**, which is also a well known dataset in RS research that considers
720 heterogeneous item profiling (Cantador et al., 2011). From this dataset the
721 qualitative attributes genre, director, country; the quantitative audience
722 score; and the year, are used for representing a multivalued item profile.
723 In the case of the year, operations like average or mode have no sense, and
724 therefore we represent it as a qualitative value. Furthermore, in this case
725 we execute our evaluation with the first 300 users in the dataset.

726 In both cases we use the same data employed by Pérez-Almaguer et al.
727 (2021), which is the former work used a base for the development of the current
728 proposal, and that will be compared with our work in the next section. Such
729 use of the same data, guarantees a fair comparison of both approaches.

730 *5.2. Evaluation metric*

731 In order to evaluate the proposals, it will be considered the precision
732 metric, which has been used previously for evaluating the top n item
733 recommendation task in group recommender systems (Baltrunas et al., 2010;
734 Kaššák et al., 2016). Here it is important to point out that this metric is used
735 in two different scenarios: 1) in the dataset building stage of the decision tree
736 induction process for identifying which aggregation scheme performs the best
737 for each group, and 2) in the core CB-GRS approach that already integrates
738 the dynamic selection process, to evaluate the recommendation accuracy of the
739 current group. In the next future, other relevant metrics such as NDCG will
740 be also used; however at this stage we decided to be focused in one specific
741 metric considering its dual use across the framework. A parallel use of a
742 second metric here, goes beyond our current objective, which is the
743 presentation of a proof-of-concept of the dynamic aggregation approach in
744 GRS. In addition, it would lead to further issues such as determining which
745 metrics use in the first and the second mentioned scenarios, and how to
746 evaluate their effects in the recommendation performance.

For each list of top n recommended items, Precision (Gunawardana & Shani, 2009) is defined as the ratio between the amount of recommended items

that were actually preferred by the current user, and the overall amount of recommended items (in this case k).

$$Precision = \frac{|recommended\ items \cap preferred\ items|}{|recommended\ items|} \quad (27)$$

747 To complete the Precision task, all the items in the test set of each user are
 748 taken into account for recommendation generation, in a similar way to
 749 previous works focused on the same recommendation task (Baltrunas et al.,
 750 2010; De Pessemier et al., 2014; Park et al., 2016). In addition, for Precision
 751 calculation it is used a preference threshold $pref$ that considers preferred
 752 items as those that verify $r_{ui} \geq 4$, which is a common criteria for this
 753 threshold selection (Ricci et al., 2011).

754 5.3. Experimental protocol

755 We evaluate the proposal across the following steps (Castro et al., 2017;
 756 Gunawardana & Shani, 2009):

- 757 • Initially, the set of ratings associated to each user profile is randomly split
 758 into the user-associated training and test sets. The final training and test
 759 sets, are then built by merging the training and test set of each user.
- 760 • We build user groups of different sizes, following a group formation criteria
 761 that will be explained below.
- 762 • For the whole training dataset composed of all the groups, we execute
 763 the procedure for getting the classification rules, supported by the fuzzy
 764 decision tree induction (Figure 6). In the current context we match the
 765 group sampling required for the tree induction, with the whole group
 766 population.
- 767 • For each group, we apply the proposed framework over the training data of
 768 their users including the dynamic selection step supported by the obtained
 769 classification rules. As result, the top n recommended items for the group
 770 are reached.
- 771 • The accuracy of the top n recommendation list is evaluated through the
 772 accuracy metric, by contrasting it with the items currently associated
 773 to each user in the test set, considering as ground truth the preferences
 774 associated to such test set. The average accuracy values for all groups are
 775 finally computed.

776 Furthermore, several approaches have been considered in the literature for
 777 group composition. Here we use a criteria that guarantees that groups'
 778 members always keep some characteristics in common (Baltrunas et al., 2010;
 779 Kaššák et al., 2016), and specifically we follow the criteria referred at Kaššák
 780 et al. (2016), that consider groups composed by individuals that have
 781 commonly rated the same set of items. Here, we regard item sets of size 5

782 located in the ratings test set, considering that in a practical experimental
783 scenario is difficult the composition of groups with a larger size, and that a size
784 below 5 does not represent a compact group able to be properly characterized
785 through the attributes proposed at the current paper (see Section 3.1).

786 We consider groups with sizes 3 and 4 members depending of each
787 experimental scenario. For each case, 20 groups that guarantee the fulfilment
788 of this criteria (Kaššák et al., 2016) are built. For each group, the top n
789 recommendation list is generated by varying n in the range [1,5] with step 1,
790 and also in the range [5,20] with step 5. This process is repeated 10 times,
791 averaging the results.

792 5.4. Exploratory study of the groups' attribute selection

793 Section 3.1 detailed the four attributes that will be used for group
794 characterization. Such attributes are 1) the minimum correlation between any
795 pair of group members, 2) the amount of ratings across the group, 3) the
796 amount of co-rated items by all the users, and 4) the rating average of the
797 group. This section will present an exploratory study of the groups' attribute
798 selection at the used datasets.

799 5.4.1. Movielens

800 Initially, Figures 11-13 present the frequency of the values of the four
801 considered attributes for all the groups in the dataset Movielens. As
802 mentioned, such attributes are: 1) the minimum correlation between any pair
803 of group members, 2) the amount of ratings across the group, 3) the amount of
804 co-rated items by all the users, and 4) the rating average of the group.

805 **Minimum correlation between group members:** In the case of the
806 attribute *minimum correlation between group members* (Figure 10), it can be
807 observed that the sampled groups present values distributed across all the
808 possible correlation values, even though a larger number of groups have
809 correlation values in the range $[-0.5,0]$. In addition, there were several groups
810 with correlation values equal to zero and one. The tendency to have a
811 balanced distribution across all the possible correlation values, guarantees in
812 advance a better attribute exploitation in the decision tree induction process
813 (see Section 3.2). In this way it guarantees that the available data would cover
814 most of the possible membership values associated to the fuzzy set *low*,
815 *medium*, and *high*, linked to the current attribute.

816 **Amount of group ratings:** In the case of the attribute *amount of group*
817 *ratings* (Figure 11), it can be observed that most of groups have an attribute
818 value in the range $[80,400]$, being concentrated in the range $[80,160]$.
819 Furthermore, it can be identified that there are several groups with a high
820 membership value associated to the *low* and *medium* fuzzy sets related to
821 such attribute (see Section 3.2).

822 **Amount of co-rated items:** Subsequently, Figure 12 shows the behavior
823 of the attribute *amount of co-rated items* across all groups. As could be initially
824 expected, there is a strong tendency in the groups to have low values of this

Figure 10: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *minimum correlation between group members*, across all the sampled groups in Movielens 100K

Figure 11: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *amount of group ratings*, across all the sampled groups in Movielens 100K

825 attribute. Specifically, most of the explored groups have an amount of co-
 826 rated items under four. This imbalance in the frequency behavior suggests
 827 the necessity of exploring further membership functions in the future, beyond
 828 the function presented at Section 3.2, to be used in scenarios like this one.
 829 Furthermore, in the next Section 5.4.2, it will be showed how the frequency
 830 values of this attribute for composed groups at the HetRec dataset is different
 831 in relation to the presented here for Movielens.

832 **Rating average of the group:** Finally, Figure 13 shows the behavior of the
 833 attribute *rating average of the group* across all groups. Here, most of groups lie
 834 in the range $[3, 3.8]$, presenting also some imbalance even though it is not as large
 835 as in the attribute *amount of co-rated ratings*. Despite of such imbalance, here
 836 the generic fuzzy sets presented in Section 3.2 for characterizing these values,
 837 are able to discriminate among groups with high membership values for the sets
 838 *medium* and *high*. We remark that the use of more sophisticated membership
 839 functions as in Yera et al. (2016), tied to some specific attributes distribution
 840 values, are out of the scope of this paper.

Figure 12: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *amount of co-rated items*, across all the sampled groups in Movielens 100K

Figure 13: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *rating average of the group*, across all the sampled groups in Movielens 100K

841 *5.4.2. HetRec*

842 This subsection presents the frequency of the values of the four considered
 843 attributes (Section 3.1), for all the groups in the dataset HetRec using the same
 844 scheme previously used for the other dataset (Section 5.4.1). Initially, Figures
 845 15-17 present the frequency of the values of the four attributes for all the groups.

846 **Minimum correlation between group members:** In the case of the
 847 attribute *minimum correlation between group members*, Figure 14 presents a
 848 behavior that is similar to the associated to the Movielens 100K dataset at
 849 Figure 10, in the sense that the groups contained values distributed across all
 850 the possible correlation values, also with several groups with correlation values
 851 equal to zero and one. However, in contrast to the former dataset, in this case
 852 there is an important amount of positive correlation values; lying in the range
 853 $[0, 0.3]$.

854 **Amount of group ratings:** In the case of the attribute *amount of group*
 855 *ratings* (Figure 15), it can be observed that most of groups have an attribute
 856 value in the range $[20, 800]$, being common the frequency of groups in the range
 857 $[300, 400]$. Therefore, such groups will have a higher membership value to the
 858 fuzzy set *low*, and a lower membership value to the fuzzy set *medium*, associated
 859 to this attribute (see Section 3.2). These results are different to the behavior of

Figure 14: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *minimum correlation between group members*, across all the sampled groups in HetRec

Figure 15: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *amount of group ratings*, across all the sampled groups in HetRec

860 the previously analyzed MovieLens dataset, where the amount of ratings of the
 861 built groups, were more distributed across the minimum and maximum possible
 862 value for the attribute.

863 **Amount of co-rated items:** Subsequently, Figure 16 presents the
 864 frequency values associated to the attribute *amount of co-rated items*. It is
 865 worthy to note that in contrast to the MovieLens dataset (Figure 12), the
 866 amount of co-rated items for groups was not concentrated in the smallest
 867 possible values, and here it is reported several groups with values in the range
 868 [1,18]. However, it is also reported an important imbalance across values, and
 869 for this reason other membership functions for the currently defined fuzzy sets
 870 (see Section 3.2) should be explored in the future for this kind of attributes, as
 871 was also pointed out in MovieLens.

872 **Rating average of the group:** Finally, Figure 13 shows the behavior
 873 of the attribute *rating average of the group* across all groups. In contrast to
 874 the MovieLens dataset, here all the values are concentrated in the well-defined
 875 range [2.85,4]. Therefore, the proposed fuzzy sets are able to represent better
 876 each group particularities across the group’s membership values to the sets *low*,
 877 *medium*, and *high*. Here the higher frequencies were associated to a rating
 878 average around 3.45.

Figure 16: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *amount of co-rated items*, across all the sampled groups in HetRec

Figure 17: Histogram presenting the frequency of the values for the attribute *rating average of the group*, across all the sampled groups in HetRec

879 Overall, this exploratory study suggested that the identified attributes are
 880 able to discriminate among groups, and that such discrimination can be useful
 881 for selecting the most appropriate CB-GRS approach.

882 5.5. Results

883 This section presents the results of the evaluation of the proposal, in both
 884 Movielens 100K and MovieTweeting datasets. This evaluation is focused on: 1)
 885 identifying the impact of the new proposal that incorporates the fuzzy decision
 886 tree approach, by comparing its performance with previous baselines that do
 887 not consider the fuzzy decision tree, and 2) measuring the performance of the
 888 proposal when one of the four identified group attributes (see Section 3.1) is not
 889 taken into account for the decision tree building. This second criteria contribute
 890 to quantify the effect of each individual group attribute, in the full proposal.

891 Specifically, seven approaches will be evaluated:

- 892 • The current proposal, detailed at Section 3 (*dyn*).
- 893 • The current proposal, detailed at Section 3, but without considering the
 894 attribute *minimum correlation between any pair of group members* (*dyn*
 895 not *M*).

top N	1	2	3	4	5	10	15	20
Approaches that does not consider the fuzzy decision tree induction process								
avg (baseline)	0.5787	0.5844	0.5788	0.5684	0.5740	0.5681	0.5628	0.563
min (baseline)	0.5813	0.5725	0.5829	0.5841	0.5845	0.5754	0.5708	0.5713
Approaches incorporating the fuzzy decision tree induction process								
dyn	0.6025	0.5806	0.5879	0.5844	0.5855	0.5760	0.5686	0.5685
dyn not AV	0.600	0.5788	0.5850	0.5838	0.5850	0.5763	0.5698	0.5693
dyn not C	0.5838	0.5844	0.5879	0.5841	0.5850	0.5744	0.5669	0.5651
dyn not M	0.5963	0.5763	0.5846	0.5853	0.5873	0.5785	0.5712	0.5712
dyn not A	0.5925	0.5725	0.5825	0.5813	0.5833	0.5769	0.5703	0.5699

Table 8: Evaluation of the proposal and comparison with baselines avg and min, presented at (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021). Movielens 100K dataset. Precision value.

- 896 • The current proposal, detailed at Section 3, but without considering the
897 attribute *amount of ratings of the group* (*dyn not A*).
- 898 • The current proposal, detailed at Section 3, but without considering the
899 attribute *amount of co-rated items* (*dyn not C*).
- 900 • The current proposal, detailed at Section 3, but without considering the
901 attribute *rating average* (*dyn not AV*).
- 902 • As baseline, the former CB-GRS based on recommendation aggregation
903 and user-item matching values (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021), always using
904 average aggregation (*avg*) and without the use of the fuzzy decision tree.
- 905 • As baseline, the former CB-GRS based on recommendation aggregation
906 and user-item matching values (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021), always using
907 minimum aggregation (*min*), and without the use of the fuzzy decision
908 tree.

909 5.5.1. Movielens

910 This subsection presents the results associated to the dataset Movielens
911 100K.

912 Here the proposal is evaluated considering as parameters $\theta_r = 0.9$ and $\theta_n =$
913 0.01 , i.e. the stop conditions are executed once the relative frequency of some
914 class in the current node is equal or higher that 0.9 , or when the cardinality
915 of the set as such node is under 0.01 , see Section 3.2. Further executions were
916 performed for other values of θ_r and θ_n , reporting here the values that lead to
917 a better performance.

918 The results are obtained for groups of size 4; and the size of the top n
919 recommendation lists were in the range $[1, 5]$ with step 1, and $[5, 20]$ with step
920 5.

921 Table 8 shows these results, being differentiated those associated with our
922 proposal that incorporates the fuzzy decision tree induction, and those
923 associated to the baseline that does not consider it. Here it is presented that
924 for 6 of the 8 experimental scenarios the proposal is able to outperform the

925 baselines, and for $n=2$ and $n=20$, it reaches a similar behavior to the average
926 and minimum approach respectively. Furthermore, it is relevant to mention
927 that while for $n=1$ and $n=3$ the best performance is reached when the four
928 group attributes are used, for the other scenarios it is reached with the
929 exclusion of some attribute. Specifically, for $n=2$ the best result was obtained
930 with the exclusion of the attribute *amount of co-rated items*. In addition, for
931 $n=\{4,5,10,15\}$, the best results were obtained with the exclusion of the
932 attribute *minimum correlation between any pair of members*, even though the
933 values of this attribute in the groups, have a tendency to a fair distribution
934 across all the possible attribute values (Figure 10)

935 Overall, the results evidence that for the Movielens dataset, the proposal
936 is able to identify the best aggregation function to use in a CB-GRS based
937 on recommendation aggregation, considering that it notably outperforms two
938 baselines that always use the average and minimum aggregation.

939 5.5.2. *HetRec*

940 This subsection presents the results associated to the dataset HetRec.

941 The proposal is evaluated considering as parameters $\theta_r = 0.9$ and $\theta_n = 0.01$,
942 and compared with the baselines also considered for the Movielens dataset. In
943 a similar way to Movielens, further executions were performed for other values
944 of θ_r and θ_n , reporting here the values that lead to a better performance.

945 The results are obtained for groups of size 3 considering that larger groups
946 were not able to obtain due to the sparsity of the dataset. Furthermore, the
947 sizes of the top n recommendations lists were in the range $[1,5]$ with step 1, and
948 $[5,20]$ with step 5.

949 Table 9 presents the evaluation results, being differentiated those associated
950 with our proposal, and those associated to the baseline that does not consider
951 the fuzzy decision tree induction. In this case, for all the experimental scenarios,
952 the new proposal outperforms the baselines. Specifically, for $n = \{3,4,5\}$ the use
953 of the four group attributes for building the fuzzy decision tree leads to the best
954 performance. Furthermore, for $n = \{1,2,15\}$, such performance was achieved by
955 discarding the attribute *rating average*, and for two cases ($n = \{10,20\}$) it was
956 achieved by discarding the *amount of co-rated items*.

957 Overall, in this dataset is more clear the superiority of the proposal over the
958 baselines, in relation to the previous dataset Movielens. Furthermore, it is also
959 worthy to remark that there was not a specific group feature which exclusion
960 globally leads to a performance improvement, across the different sizes of the
961 recommendation lists.

962 5.6. *Final discussion*

963 This paper has introduced a content-based GRS framework, based on
964 recommendation aggregation, and focused on performing a dynamic selection
965 of the most appropriate aggregation functions according to the nature of the
966 active group. The development of the proposal as well as the experimentation,
967 lead to the following findings:

top N	1	2	3	4	5	10	15	20
Approaches that does not consider the fuzzy decision tree induction process								
avg (baseline)	0.5050	0.5075	0.5039	0.5000	0.5013	0.4957	0.4952	0.4943
min (baseline)	0.5700	0.5483	0.5417	0.5358	0.5297	0.5080	0.5024	0.4994
Approaches incorporating the fuzzy decision tree induction process								
dyn	0.5817	0.5483	0.5422	0.5363	0.5299	0.5083	0.5029	0.4989
dyn not AV	0.5833	0.5492	0.5406	0.5350	0.5277	0.5080	0.5031	0.5000
dyn not C	0.5817	0.5467	0.5367	0.5333	0.5263	0.5090	0.5024	0.5003
dyn not M	0.5700	0.5500	0.5422	0.5354	0.5280	0.5083	0.5031	0.4993
dyn not A	0.5783	0.5483	0.5417	0.5358	0.5297	0.5080	0.5024	0.4994

Table 9: Evaluation of the proposal and comparison with baselines avg and min, presented at (Pérez-Almaguer et al., 2021). HetRec dataset. Precision value.

- 968 • The analysis of the literature related to content-based GRS, suggested that
969 as far as we know, there is not a direct antecedent focused on the use of
970 machine learning techniques, to learn knowledge from the groups' behavior
971 and therefore using this knowledge for improving the recommendation
972 generation for such groups.
- 973 • The exploratory analysis of the four group attributes considered in this
974 work, which are the minimum correlation between any pair of group
975 members, the amount of ratings across the group, the amount of
976 co-rated items by all the users, and the rating average of the group;
977 shows that they are able to characterize groups' behavior, even though it
978 was with a larger or lesser success depending on the nature of the data.
- 979 • As could be expected, an exploratory analysis using frequency
980 histograms, shows that there are different imbalance levels across the
981 groups attributes. In cases such as the minimum correlation between
982 group members in both datasets, it can be observed some balance across
983 the groups regarding the frequency values of this attribute. In contrast,
984 in other cases such as the amount of co-rated items or the amount of
985 groups' ratings in HetRec, there are many groups that share the same or
986 similar attribute values. This fact would need the introduction in this
987 framework, of more sophisticated membership functions beyond the
988 proposed in Figure 8, for a better characterization of the data in the
989 fuzzy decision tree induction process.
- 990 • The experimental results evidence a positive performance for MovieLens
991 100K and HetRec datasets. In both cases, the new proposal leads to an
992 improvement of the recommendation performance, showing the suitability
993 of our approach focused on using a fuzzy decision tree for dynamically
994 selecting the most appropriate aggregation function in a CB-GRS scenario,
995 based on the groups' features. Specifically, it was evidenced that a CB-
996 GRS with such dynamic selection, outperforms two CB-GRSs that always
997 use average and minimum respectively, as aggregation operators.
- 998 • From a general viewpoint, the results show that the incorporation of a

999 fuzzy decision tree in a content-based group recommendation model, for
1000 supporting the recommendation generation process, is able to improve the
1001 recommendation generation performance. In this way, for the Movielens
1002 dataset it was able to reach a Precision value up to 0.6025, while the
1003 baselines that does not use the fuzzy decision tree reach up to 0.5845. In
1004 the HetRec dataset, the proposal reaches a Precision up to 0.5833, while
1005 the baselines reach up to 0.5700.

- 1006 • Overall, the experimental results show that the proposal can serve as a
1007 starting point for developing a new research branch focused on the
1008 dynamic selection of the most appropriate components of a GRS
1009 framework, taking as input some attributes of the group.

1010 5.7. Future works

1011 The aim of this research paper is to be an starting point in the research
1012 branch related to the dynamic selection of the components of a GRS, as it has
1013 been previously commented. At this moment, the next future work to continue
1014 this research would be:

- 1015 • The exploration of more sophisticate t-norms, t-conorms, and
1016 membership functions for the fuzzy sets *low*, *medium*, and *high* (Figure
1017 8), that reflect better the nature of data. In the current work, we have
1018 used the well-recognized triangular membership functions as the basic
1019 approach. However, they could not be the most appropriate for some
1020 scenarios. As future work it will be explored the role of trapezoidal and
1021 sigmoidal membership functions for boosting or decreasing the effect of
1022 some group's attributes values, in the group's membership to the nodes
1023 in the induced decision tree. Furthermore, other t-norms (e.g. product)
1024 and t-conorms (e.g. probabilistic sum), will be also explored (Zadeh,
1025 1965; Dubois & Prade, 1978).
- 1026 • The use of further schemes for calculating the relevance of the item
1027 profiles for each corresponding user, in the inner content-based
1028 recommendation approach. Being use in the current scenario the cosine
1029 measure as the reference approach (see Section 2.1), in the next works it
1030 will be considered more sophisticated schemes incorporating further
1031 knowledge sources (e.g. ontologies, linked open data cloud, other
1032 graph-based structures, etc) (de Gemmis et al., 2015).
- 1033 • The use of feature engineering approaches for a better characterization of
1034 the identified features, as well as the extracting of other features. Feature
1035 management comprises a wide range of techniques that could be applied
1036 here, such as feature weighting, or the discovery of latent features (Koren
1037 et al., 2009).
- 1038 • The use of other supervised classifiers beyond the fuzzy decision tree-
1039 based. Fuzzy decision trees have been currently used as a white-box and

1040 effective classifier. However, it is interesting to explore here other well-
1041 recognized alternatives, such as multi-classifiers, support vector machines,
1042 or deep learning-based classifiers (Arrieta et al., 2020).

- 1043 • The use of the presented framework in other GRS scenarios, beyond
1044 content-based group recommendation. Here, a primary direction is the
1045 evaluation of the proposal in a collaborative filtering-based GRS.

1046 6. Conclusions

1047 This paper presents a novel framework for content-based group
1048 recommendation, which main feature is the dynamic selection of the most
1049 appropriate aggregation function, for the recommendation aggregation step.

1050 Specifically, it is focused on proposing the use of four attributes for
1051 characterizing groups in content-based GRS. Such attributes are the minimum
1052 correlation between any pair of group members, the amount of ratings across
1053 the group, the amount of co-rated items by all the users, and the rating
1054 average of the group. Specifically the proposal is focused on building a fuzzy
1055 decision tree that helps to match such attributes of a specific group, with the
1056 best aggregation function (average or minimum), that can be use for such
1057 group in the individual recommendation aggregation step for improving the
1058 recommendation performance.

1059 The proposal is evaluated by an experimental protocol over well-known
1060 datasets. The results particularly show that it is able to outperform the
1061 baseline for most of all scenarios in the Movielens and HetRec datasets.
1062 Furthermore, it was also developed an exploratory analysis of the values of
1063 such attributes in all the groups used in the experiments, showing different
1064 imbalance degrees that could affect the application of the proposal in a higher
1065 or lesser extent.

1066 From a practical viewpoint, our work provides a methodology initially
1067 presented for the content-based group recommendation context but that can
1068 be also used in other GRSs, in order to guarantee a more dynamic
1069 construction of the recommendation architecture, that could result in an
1070 improvement of the recommendation accuracy. Furthermore, the nature of the
1071 proposal would allow its use in a higher dimension and dense scenarios,
1072 considering that its phases tend to have a linear dependency on the dimension
1073 of the data, and that most of such phases can be executed in an offline mode
1074 for saving computational cost.

1075 The next future work to be developed, already pointed out in the previous
1076 section, comprises some goals such as the use of feature engineering approaches
1077 for a better characterization of groups, the use of more sophisticate membership
1078 functions that represent better the nature of the data, and the use of other
1079 supervised classifiers beyond the fuzzy decision tree.

1080 **Acknowledgements**

1081 This work was supported by the Deanship of Scientific Research (DSR), King
1082 Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, under Grant Kep-15-611-42.

1083 **References**

1084 **References**

- 1085 Adomavicius, G., & Tuzhilin, A. T. (2005). Toward the next generation
1086 of recommender systems: A survey of the state-of-the-art and possible
1087 extensions. *IEEE Trans. on Knowl. Data Eng.*, *17*, 734–749.
- 1088 Aizawa, A. (2003). An information-theoretic perspective of tf-idf measures.
1089 *Information Processing and Management*, *39*, 45–65.
- 1090 Arrieta, A. B., Díaz-Rodríguez, N., Del Ser, J., Bennetot, A., Tabik, S.,
1091 Barbado, A., García, S., Gil-López, S., Molina, D., Benjamins, R. et al.
1092 (2020). Explainable artificial intelligence (xai): Concepts, taxonomies,
1093 opportunities and challenges toward responsible ai. *Information Fusion*, *58*,
1094 82–115.
- 1095 Baltrunas, L., Kaminskas, M., Ludwig, B., Moling, O., Ricci, F., Aydin, A.,
1096 Lüke, K.-H., & Schwaiger, R. (2011). InCarMusic: Context-Aware Music
1097 Recommendations in a Car E-Commerce and Web Technologies. chapter 8.
1098 (pp. 89–100). Springer Berlin Heidelberg volume 85 of *Lecture Notes in*
1099 *Business Information Processing*.
- 1100 Baltrunas, L., Makcinskas, T., & Ricci, F. (2010). Group recommendations
1101 with rank aggregation and collaborative filtering. In *Proceedings of the 4th*
1102 *ACM Conference on Recommender Systems RecSys '10* (pp. 119–126). New
1103 York, NY, USA: ACM.
- 1104 Boratto, L., Carta, S., & Fenu, G. (2015). Discovery and representation of the
1105 preferences of automatically detected groups: Exploiting the link between
1106 group modeling and clustering. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, *24*,
1107 833–848.
- 1108 Cantador, I., Brusilovsky, P., & Kuflik, T. (2011). 2nd workshop on
1109 information heterogeneity and fusion in recommender systems (hetrec 2011).
1110 In *Proceedings of the 5th ACM conference on Recommender systems RecSys*
1111 *2011*. New York, NY, USA: ACM.
- 1112 Castro, J., Barranco, M. J., Rodríguez, R. M., & Martínez, L. (2018a). Group
1113 recommendations based on hesitant fuzzy sets. *International Journal of*
1114 *Intelligent Systems*, *33*, 2058–2077.
- 1115 Castro, J., Lu, J., Zhang, G., Dong, Y., & Martínez, L. (2018b). Opinion
1116 dynamics-based group recommender systems. *IEEE Transactions on Systems,*
1117 *Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, *48*, 2394–2406.

- 1118 Castro, J., Quesada, F. J., Palomares, I., & Martínez, L. (2015). A consensus-
1119 driven group recommender system. *International Journal of Intelligent*
1120 *Systems*, *30*, 887–906.
- 1121 Castro, J., Rodríguez, R. M., & Barranco, M. J. (2014). Weighting of features in
1122 content-based filtering with entropy and dependence measures. *International*
1123 *Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, *7*, 80–89.
- 1124 Castro, J., Yera, R., Alzahrani, A. A., Sanchez, P., Barranco, M., & Martínez,
1125 L. (2019). A big data semantic driven context aware recommendation method
1126 for question-answer items. *IEEE Access*, *7*, 182664–182678.
- 1127 Castro, J., Yera, R., & Martínez, L. (2017). An empirical study of natural noise
1128 management in group recommendation systems. *Decision Support Systems*,
1129 *94*, 1 – 11.
- 1130 Castro, J., Yera, R., & Martínez, L. (2018c). A fuzzy approach for natural
1131 noise management in group recommender systems. *Expert Systems with*
1132 *Applications*, *94*, 237–249.
- 1133 Cui, Z., Xu, X., Fei, X., Cai, X., Cao, Y., Zhang, W., & Chen, J. (2020).
1134 Personalized recommendation system based on collaborative filtering for iot
1135 scenarios. *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing*, *13*, 685–695.
- 1136 Dara, S., Chowdary, C., & Kumar, C. (2020). A survey on group recommender
1137 systems. *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, *54*, 271–295.
- 1138 De Pessemier, T., Dhondt, J., Vanhecke, K., & Martens, L. (2015a).
1139 Travelwithfriends: a hybrid group recommender system for travel
1140 destinations. In *Workshop on tourism recommender systems (touRS15), in*
1141 *conjunction with the 9th ACM conference on recommender systems (recsys*
1142 *2015)* (pp. 51–60).
- 1143 De Pessemier, T., Dhondt, J., Vanhecke, K., & Martens, L. (2015b).
1144 Travelwithfriends: a hybrid group recommender system for travel
1145 destinations. In *Workshop on tourism recommender systems (touRS15), in*
1146 *conjunction with the 9th ACM conference on recommender systems (recsys*
1147 *2015)* (pp. 51–60).
- 1148 De Pessemier, T., Dooms, S., & Martens, L. (2014). Comparison of group
1149 recommendation algorithms. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, *72*, 2497–
1150 2541.
- 1151 Dubois, D., & Prade, H. (1978). Operations on fuzzy numbers. *International*
1152 *Journal of systems science*, *9*, 613–626.
- 1153 Ekstrand, M. D., Riedl, J. T., & Konstan, J. A. (2011). Collaborative
1154 filtering recommender systems. *Foundations and Trends in Human-Computer*
1155 *Interaction*, *4*, 81–173.

- 1156 Felfernig, A., Boratto, L., Stettinger, M., & Tkalčič, M. (2018). *Group*
1157 *recommender systems: An introduction*. Springer.
- 1158 Francesco Ricci, B. S., Lior Rokach (Ed.) (2015). *Recommender Systems*
1159 *Handbook*. (2nd ed.). Springer US.
- 1160 de Gemmis, M., Lops, P., Musto, C., Narducci, F., & Semeraro, G. (2015).
1161 Semantics-aware content-based recommender systems. In F. Ricci, L. Rokach,
1162 & B. Shapira (Eds.), *Recommender Systems Handbook* (pp. 119–159).
1163 Springer US.
- 1164 Gunawardana, A., & Shani, G. (2009). A Survey of Accuracy Evaluation Metrics
1165 of Recommendation Tasks. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, *10*, 2935–
1166 2962.
- 1167 Harper, F. M., & Konstan, J. A. (2015). The movielens datasets: History and
1168 context. *ACM Trans. Interact. Intell. Syst.*, *5*, 19:1–19:19.
- 1169 Isinkaye, F. O. (2021). Matrix factorization in recommender systems:
1170 Algorithms, applications, and peculiar challenges. *IETE Journal of Research*,
1171 (pp. 1–14).
- 1172 Jankiewicz, P., Kyrashchuk, L., Sienkowski, P., & Wójcik, M. (2019). Boosting
1173 algorithms for a session-based, context-aware recommender system in an
1174 online travel domain. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on ACM Recommender*
1175 *Systems Challenge* (pp. 1–5).
- 1176 Janusz, A., Stawicki, S., Drewniak, M., Ciebiera, K., Ślęzak, D., & Stencel, K.
1177 (2018). How to match jobs and candidates—a recruitment support system
1178 based on feature engineering and advanced analytics. In *International*
1179 *Conference on Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in*
1180 *Knowledge-Based Systems* (pp. 503–514). Springer.
- 1181 Kantarci, S., & Nasibov, E. (2018). A fuzzy id3 induction for linguistic data
1182 sets. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, *33*, 858–878.
- 1183 Kaššák, O., Kompan, M., & Bieliková, M. (2016). Personalized hybrid
1184 recommendation for group of users: Top-n multimedia recommender.
1185 *Information Processing & Management*, *52*, 459–477.
- 1186 Koren, Y., Bell, R., & Volinsky, C. (2009). Matrix factorization techniques for
1187 recommender systems. *Computer*, *42*, 30–37.
- 1188 Lops, P., Gemmis, M., & Semeraro, G. (2011). Content-based recommender
1189 systems: State of the art and trends. In *Recommender Systems Handbook*
1190 chapter 3. (pp. 73–105). Springer US.
- 1191 Nguyen, T. N., & Ricci, F. (2018). A chat-based group recommender system
1192 for tourism. *Information Technology & Tourism*, *18*, 5–28.

- 1193 Nilashi, M., bin Ibrahim, O., Ithnin, N., & Sarmin, N. H. (2015). A multi-
1194 criteria collaborative filtering recommender system for the tourism domain
1195 using expectation maximization (em) and pca-anfis. *Electronic Commerce*
1196 *Research and Applications*, *14*, 542–562.
- 1197 Park, C., Kim, D., Oh, J., & Yu, H. (2016). Using user trust network to improve
1198 top-k recommendation. *Information Science*, *374*, 100–114.
- 1199 Pazzani, M., & Billsus, D. (2007). Content-Based Recommendation Systems.
1200 *The Adaptive Web*, *4321*, 325–341.
- 1201 Pedrycz, W. (1993). *Fuzzy control and fuzzy systems*. Research Studies Press
1202 Ltd.
- 1203 Pera, M., & Ng, Y. (2013). A group recommender for movies based on content
1204 similarity and popularity. *Information Processing and Management*, *49*, 673–
1205 687.
- 1206 Pera, M., & Ng, Y. K. (2014). Automating readers advisory to make book
1207 recommendations for k-12 readers. In *Proceedings of the ACM Conference on*
1208 *Recommender Systems RecSys '14* (pp. 9–16). ACM.
- 1209 Pérez-Almaguer, Y., Yera, R., Alzahrani, A. A., & Martínez, L. (2021).
1210 Content-based group recommender systems: A general taxonomy and further
1211 improvements. *Expert Systems with Applications*, *184*, 115444.
- 1212 Quijano-Sanchez, L., Recio-Garcia, J. A., & Diaz-Agudo, B. (2014).
1213 An architecture and functional description to integrate social behaviour
1214 knowledge into group recommender systems. *Applied intelligence*, *40*, 732–
1215 748.
- 1216 Ricci, F., Rokach, L., & Shapira, B. (2011). Recommender systems handbook.
1217 In F. Ricci, L. Rokach, B. Shapira, & P. B. Kantor (Eds.), *Recommender*
1218 *Systems Handbook* chapter 1. (pp. 1–35). Springer.
- 1219 Seo, Y.-D., Kim, Y.-G., Lee, E., Seol, K.-S., & Baik, D.-K. (2018). An enhanced
1220 aggregation method considering deviations for a group recommendation.
1221 *Expert Systems with Applications*, *93*, 299–312.
- 1222 Son, L. H. (2015). Hu-fcf++: A novel hybrid method for the new user cold-
1223 start problem in recommender systems. *Engineering Applications of Artificial*
1224 *Intelligence*, *41*, 207 – 222.
- 1225 Umanol, M., Okamoto, H., Hatono, I., Tamura, H., Kawachi, F., Umedzu,
1226 S., & Kinoshita, J. (1994). Fuzzy decision trees by fuzzy id3 algorithm
1227 and its application to diagnosis systems. In *Proceedings of 1994 IEEE 3rd*
1228 *International Fuzzy Systems Conference* (pp. 2113–2118). IEEE.
- 1229 Wang, J., Jiang, Y., Sun, J., Liu, Y., & Liu, X. (2018). Group recommendation
1230 based on a bidirectional tensor factorization model. *World Wide Web*, *21*,
1231 961–984.

- 1232 Xie, J., Leishman, S., Tian, L., Lisuk, D., Koo, S., & Blume, M. (2012). Feature
1233 engineering in user’s music preference prediction. In *Proceedings of KDD Cup*
1234 *2011* (pp. 183–197). PMLR.
- 1235 Yalcin, E., Ismailoglu, F., & Bilge, A. (2021). An entropy empowered hybridized
1236 aggregation technique for group recommender systems. *Expert Systems with*
1237 *Applications*, *166*, 114111.
- 1238 Yera, R., Alzahrani, A. A., & Martínez, L. (2019). A food recommender system
1239 considering nutritional information and user preferences. *IEEE Access*, *7*,
1240 96695–96711.
- 1241 Yera, R., Castro, J., & Martínez, L. (2016). A fuzzy model for managing natural
1242 noise in recommender systems. *Applied Soft Computing*, *40*, 187 – 198.
- 1243 Yera, R., & Martínez, L. (2017a). Fuzzy tools in recommender systems: A
1244 survey. *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, *10*,
1245 776–803.
- 1246 Yera, R., & Martínez, L. (2017b). A recommendation approach for
1247 programming online judges supported by data preprocessing techniques.
1248 *Applied Intelligence*, *47*, 277–290.
- 1249 Zadeh, L. A. (1965). Fuzzy sets. *Information and control*, *8*, 338–353.
- 1250 Zeeshan, Z., Bhatti, U. A., Memon, W. H., Ali, S., Nawaz, S. A., Nizamani,
1251 M. M., Mehmood, A., Bhatti, M. A., Shoukat, M. U. et al. (2021). Feature-
1252 based multi-criteria recommendation system using a weighted approach with
1253 ranking correlation. *Intelligent Data Analysis*, *25*, 1013–1029.
- 1254 Zhang, Y. (2016). Grorec: a group-centric intelligent recommender system
1255 integrating social, mobile and big data technologies. *IEEE Transactions on*
1256 *Services Computing*, *9*, 786–795.